

DISAC

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Abstract

This document presents the final architecture proposed by the 6G-DISAC project to advance the state of the art in Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) through the introduction of the concept of the Distributed ISAC framework for 6G. Building upon the initial work outlined in the preliminary DISAC architecture, which identified key challenges and proposed several enablers, this report proposes several extensions to the initial architecture. It emphasizes the role of semantics within the architecture and, in particular, to support multi-modal sensing, where alongside ISAC-based sensing, devices such as cameras, LiDAR and others are integrated.

The document discusses the role of User Equipment (UE) as a sensing device and explores the interactions of those UEs with various architectural components, with a special emphasis on orchestration. It also details several paradigms for computation and data transmission at sensing nodes and examines their implications for the overall architecture.

Furthermore, the DISAC architecture is contextualized within ongoing efforts by Standard Development Organisations (SDOs) and related SNS projects. Finally, the report consolidates all proposed enablers and extensions, providing a comprehensive overview of the complete Distributed ISAC framework.

Keywords

6G; Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC); Distributed ISAC; distributed processing; DISAC architecture; semantic communications; semantic RAN; DISAC enablers.

Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

3D	Three Dimensional
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
ACK	ACKnowledgement
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AoA	Angle of Arrival
BP	Belief Propagation
BS	Base Station
CFAR	Constant False Alarm Rate
CFR	Channel Frequency Response
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
CP-OFDM	Cyclic Prefix-Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
CSePF	Central Sensing Processing Function
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications
DISAC	Distributed Intelligent Sensing and Communication
DL	Deep Learning
D-MIMO	Distributed MIMO
DU	Distributed Unit
ELAA	Extremely Large Aperture Antennas
FC	Fusion centre
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FoV	Field of View
IoT	Internet of Things
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LLM	Large Language Models
LSePF	Local Sensing Processing Function
Ma-MIMO	Massive MIMO
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MINN	Metasurfaces-Integrated Neural Network
ML	Machine Learning
MLLM	Multi-modal Large Language Models

mMTC	massive Machine-Type Communications
MTT	Multi-Target-Tracking
MUSIC	MUltiple Signal Classification
N3IWF	Non-3GPP Interworking Function
NCAL	Network-Centric Application Layer
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NF	Network Function
NFC	Near-Field Communications
NFL	Network Functions Layer
NN	Neural Network
NR	New Radio
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
PMBM	Poisson multi-Bernoulli mixture
QoS	Quality of Service
RAD	Range-Angle-Doppler
RAN	Radio Access Network
RF	Radio Frequency
RFS	Random Finite Set
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
RU	Radio Unit
SAW	Semantic-aware Adaptive Waveform
SDLA	Semantic Deep Learning Analyzer
SDO	Standards Development Organisation
SEF	Sensing Exposure Function
SeMF	Sensing Management Function
SePF	Sensing Processing Function
SESM	Semantic Edge Slicing Module
SLAM	Simultaneous localization and mapping
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
S-RIC	Semantic RAN Intelligent Controller
SRx	Sensing Receiver
SSA	Sensing Service Area
SSFR	Semantic Sensing Fusion and Representation
SSG	Semantic Sensing Goals
SSO	Semantic Sensing Orchestration
ST	Sensing Target
STA	Station

STx	Sensing Transmitter
ToA	Time of Arrival
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TRP	Transmission Reception Point
UE	User Equipment
VAE	Variational Auto-Encoders
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package
XL-MIMO	eXtremely Large-scale MIMO

1 Introduction and challenges

1.1 Introduction

The preliminary version of the DISAC architecture [6GDISAC-D22] discussed the challenges brought by distributed intelligent processing over multiple sensing nodes covering large areas and extended timeframes. Several innovative enablers were described to handle these challenges, in particular, distributed sensing processing and associated flexible data representation, support for handover of passive targets to ensure continuity of sensing services, and adaptability mechanisms to support heterogeneous devices. A preliminary analysis of the role of semantics in the architecture was also sketched out.

This final version of the DISAC architecture extends the preliminary design, delivered in [6GDISAC-D22], along two dimensions:

- It situates the proposed DISAC architecture in the ecosystem of standardization efforts and a couple of related SNS projects towards 6G.
- It deepens the study into:
 - the role of semantics on the architecture and, in particular, to support non-3GPP devices;
 - the role and the impact of UEs on the architecture;
 - the context of distributed processing, where different strategies of computation and transmission are explored, including over-the-air computation.

1.2 Definition of terms and sensing modes

1.2.1 Terminology

Several of these definitions are taken from [3GPP22.137] and [3GPP22.837].

3GPP sensing data: data derived for sensing purposes from 3GPP radio signals impacted (e.g. reflected, refracted, diffracted) by an object or environment of interest, and optionally processed within the 5G system.

Sensing Receiver (SRx): an entity (a New Radio (NR) radio access network (RAN) node or a UE) that receives the sensing signal used by the sensing service in its operation; it may or may not be co-located with a sensing transmitter.

Sensing Transmitter (STx): an entity (an NR RAN node or a UE) that sends out the sensing signal used by the sensing service in its operation; it may or may not be co-located with a sensing receiver.

Sensing group: a set of sensing transmitters and sensing receivers whose location is known and whose sensing data can be collected in a coordinated manner.

Sensing Service Area (SSA): a location area that needs to be sensed with a certain sensing service quality by deriving the characteristics of the environment and/or objects in it from the impacted (e.g. reflected, refracted, diffracted) wireless signals; it includes both indoor and outdoor environments.

Background environment: background (clutter and/or environmental) objects that are not the sensing target(s).

Sensing Management Function (SeMF): the control and management function of ISAC which takes care of receiving sensing requests from services, discovery and selection of sensing nodes (SRx, STx), negotiation of data representations, configuration of sensing nodes.

Sensing Processing Function (SePF): the data processing function for DISAC in charge of collecting measurements from SRxs, processing them based on the negotiated data representation and fusion of data from multiple SRxs (Fusion Centre role).

RIS Controller: the network element, under the network control, which manages the RIS devices in the network.

Autonomous RIS: an RIS device which is not under the network control through the RIS controller.

1.2.2 Sensing modes

Sensing modes in a network have to do with the mapping of the STx and SRx functions to the physical nodes where sensing takes place.

Monostatic sensing: a type of sensing where the STx and the SRx functions are located on the same device. This facilitates processing, given that STx and SRx may share the same clock (eliminating the need for time and frequency synchronization) and the SRx perfectly knows the transmitted signal. Moreover, since STx and SRx are on the same device, they share the same geometric frame of reference.

Bistatic sensing: a type of sensing where STx and SRx functions are physically separated from each other. In general, this makes it harder to synchronize STx and SRx. This issue can be overcome by using the line-of-sight path as a reference (in case STx and SRx locations are known) or by using a common external reference signal (e.g., from a beacon). Predetermined pilots by STx and SRx are necessary to ensure accurate estimation. Also, a common geometric frame of reference must be organized between STx and SRx.

Multi-static sensing: a type of sensing that involves several STxs and/or SRxs functions and has bistatic sensing as a special case. The same synchronization challenges as the ones associated to bistatic sensing are thus also present. In addition, signals received from various STxs must have a certain level of orthogonality with respect to SRxs configured for measurement on these STxs. In certain types of deployment, it may be necessary to ensure phase coherence between SRxs. This makes it possible to improve spatial resolution by emulating very large aperture antennas. An interesting variant is a multi-monostatic configuration which involves several STxs/SRxs each individually operating in mono-static mode and all the collected sensing data is then fused to arrive at an estimation.

3GPP study items make the distinction between UEs and Transmission Reception Points (TRPs) and their roles as STxs and/or SRxs in classifying the modes. According to 3GPP, there are six unique sensing modes: TRP monostatic, TRP-TRP bistatic, TRP-UE bistatic, UE-TRP bistatic, UE-UE bistatic, UE monostatic. These may be extended to multi-static modes by adding additional UEs and/or TRPs to the above six basic modes.

1.3 Document structure

In section 2, the work being done either by standards bodies or by other SNS projects on ISAC architecture is reviewed. Section 3 describes some investigated extensions to the preliminary DISAC architecture. The final section summarises the conclusion on the architecture work in the 6G-DISAC project.

2 ISAC architecture: inputs from standardization and SNS projects

This section reviews the progress on ISAC standardisation and evaluates its impact on the preliminary DISAC architecture proposed in [6GDISAC-D22]. The emphasis is on the two main standardisation organisations involved in ISAC at the architecture level: 3GPP and ETSI. Section 2.1 also provides a brief overview of IEEE work on ISAC.

Regarding SNS projects, the focus is on positioning the DISAC architecture in the broader context of the 6G architecture and in better understanding and applying the emerging topic of semantics to ISAC.

2.1 Standard Development Organisations (SDOs)

2.1.1 3GPP studies

ISAC is evolving significantly within 3GPP, moving towards a paradigm where cellular networks can simultaneously perform both communication and sensing functions using shared spectrum and hardware. Initially explored in extensions to 5G as a research item, 3GPP is now standardizing key aspects to enable new capabilities such as high-resolution localization, environmental mapping, gesture recognition, and presence detection, all integrated directly into the cellular infrastructure. What began as exploratory research in 5G-Advanced is now progressing towards formal standardisation, laying critical foundations that will carry forward into 6G [5GWP+25].

In 5G, SA1 has already defined a wide range of sensing use cases in [3GPP22.837], including high-resolution localization, object detection and tracking, environmental mapping and monitoring, gesture/motion recognition, and presence detection. Supporting these capabilities, 3GPP has introduced ISAC channel modelling in [3GPP38.901], extending the legacy communication stochastic channel model with sensing-specific parameters such as Radar Cross Section (RCS) of targets. RAN1 is currently enhancing these stochastic models to better support future ISAC performance studies and system design.

The sensing features envisioned for 6G will build directly on these 5G advancements and ongoing foundational work driven primarily by 3GPP RAN1. Within Release 20, sensing studies are addressing both 5G-Advanced and early 6G requirements, with near-term focus in NR Rel-20 on gNB-based monostatic sensing, particularly for UAV-related use cases (see Figure 2-1 [S2-2509973]).

Overall, this integrated approach not only reuses existing cellular deployments for a broad new set of sensing applications beyond traditional communications, thereby creating new revenue opportunities and increasing network utility, but also involves the development of new protocols, and architectural enhancements that efficiently handle the joint demands of data transmission and radio sensing.

Figure 2-1: UAV-related monostatic sensing architecture studied in 3GPP [S2-2509973].

At the time of writing this deliverable, the ISAC architecture is currently under active discussion and agreement negotiation within 3GPP. One of the key architectural considerations concerns the connectivity between the gNB and the Sensing Function (SF). Specifically, 3GPP is evaluating whether the gNB should establish a direct connection with the SF (as illustrated in Figure 2-2 [R3-258207]), where an Nx interface is defined between the gNB and the SF to facilitate the exchange of sensing-related information and coordination data [R3-258207]), or alternatively, an indirect connection via the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF). This decision will significantly influence the control signalling, latency, and deployment flexibility of future sensing-enabled networks.

Figure 2-2: Logical architecture for ISAC [R3-258207].

Another ongoing discussion within 3GPP concerns how the sensing procedure and its results should be reported. Figure 2-3 displays a proposal for sensing procedure reporting, outlining the potential signalling flow and information exchange between the involved network entities [R3-258208].

Figure 2-3: Message flow for sensing reporting [R3-258208].

Additionally, there is an active effort to reach consensus on the appropriate architectural level at which sensing should be performed, as this decision will influence both network complexity and performance in ISAC-enabled deployments. Figure 2-4 [R1-2507472] illustrates the high-level processes involved, assuming that 5G NR downlink CP-OFDM waveforms are utilised for sensing in monostatic configuration. The transmitter and receiver chains include the legacy 5G NR transceiver blocks, while the specific sensing-related processing is handled within the ISAC Periodogram Calculation blocks. Additional data refinement is performed in the post-processing blocks to enhance key performance indicators (KPIs) or reduce data overhead. As shown in Figure 2-4 sensing data can be captured at various points

- **Point A** corresponds to raw IQ samples after the divider, which are the largest set of data in size and contain complete information from the SRxs.
- **Point B** represents delay/angular/Doppler spectrum data, which is a smaller data set due to processes such as clutter suppression.
- **Point C** corresponds to an ISAC point cloud—a set of 3D spatial data points with associated reflection, power and velocity—offering a lighter yet informative representation.
- **Point D** corresponds to the target list, which is the most compact data format.

Figure 2-4: Sensing framework with functional blocks and data capture point options [R1-2507472].

The sensing data captured from these points (A, B, C and D) are sent to upper layers, such as the SF or Sensing Application/Application Function (SA/AF) as shown in Figure 2-1. An agreement on which data should be reported is still under negotiation within 3GPP.

Non-3GPP sensing data, i.e. data provided by non-3GPP sensors (e.g., video, LiDAR, sonar, WiFi) about an object or environment of interest for sensing purposes has also been addressed in 3GPP22.137. While the mechanism of these types of sensing is not considered in that specification, non-3GPP sensing data from these non-3GPP sensors, if available, can be used in 5G wireless sensing to achieve improved sensing results, or in any other way to enhance the sensing service.

Relation to DISAC architecture

The work on ISAC architecture is very much a work in progress in 3GPP and, as mentioned in the text above, there are active discussions of the study items related to architecture. The current proposals are in line with a centralised DISAC architecture. However, DISAC also offers a distributed version of the data processing which is not currently the focus of the standards but is essential for research projects. The text on the contribution [R1-2507472] on data processing is similar to the data representation proposal in [6GDISAC-D22]. The role of semantics in the architecture is out of scope for 3GPP.

2.1.2 ETSI ISG on ISAC

ETSI launched an Industry Specification Group for ISAC (ISAC ISG) in November 2023. There are currently five working groups within this ISG. Work Group (WG) 1 deals with “ISAC Use Cases and Deployment Scenarios, WG2 on “Channel Modelling, Measurements and Evaluation Methodology”, WG3 on “System and RAN Architectures for ISAC”, WG4 on “Security, Privacy, Trustworthiness and Sustainability” and the newly started WG5 on “Integration of Computing with ISAC”.

WG1 published a Group Report (GR) on use cases in March 2025 [ETSIGRISAC001]. It identifies 18 advanced use cases which go beyond the ones defined in [3GPP22.837]. WG2 published a GR on channel modelling in August 2025 [ETSIGRISAC002]. WG3 targets system and RAN architecture framework and definition for ISAC and will focus on the identified sensing types, integration levels, and deployments towards 6G. WG3 work started at the beginning of 2024 and it is still ongoing and the publication of the respective GR is expected end of 2025. It should be noted that the current work is phase 1, which implies that no specifications will be published. The nature of the work is to identify challenges and describe various potential approaches to meet these challenges.

The GR lists identified considerations and challenges which are summarized below.

- A reference model of the system architecture is provided. This is quite abstract and illustrates the entities involved in sensing and their interactions with each other.
- The separation between sensing control and processing is emphasized in this architecture as in 6G-DISAC.
- Sensing service request, data request as well as response and reports are discussed. Both data processing and data representation are examined. The latter is related to the work done in 6G-DISAC and is detailed below.
- Emphasis is given on the challenge of the volume of sensing data and the need to design efficient data collection, which is also in phase with the concerns of 6G-DISAC.
- Support for mobility of sensing devices is discussed.
- Exposure of sensing results to the entity/application which requested the sensing service.
- Discussions on provisioning are also included.
- A sensing service consumes resources for sensing. The network operator should consider how to charge the consumer for the services offered.

Then, potential approaches to the above considerations and challenges are examined. Architecture is discussed and network functions for sensing control, sensing data processing, and a sensing exposure function are proposed. In addition, mention is made of a sensing data storage function.

Partners of the 6G-DISAC project provided a contribution to WG3 in July 2024 based on the work done in [6GDISAC-D22]. The contribution is related to the challenge of handling the large volume of sensing data to be exchanged between the SRx and the sensing processing function while at the same time satisfying a wide range of use cases with varying sensing performance requirements. The contribution lists some of the potential solutions in terms of data representation and their advantages and inconveniences.

In addition to the work in WG3, the working groups on “Security, Privacy, Trustworthiness, and Sustainability” (WG4) and on “Integration of Computing with ISAC” (WG5) are both very relevant to 6G-DISAC. Neither WG has published Group reports as of November 2025. It is worth noting that the work described in section 3.3 of this deliverable is on the topic of computing in ISAC.

Relation to DISAC architecture

The general high-level architecture is similar to the one used in DISAC. The separation between control and data processing is emphasized. As noted above, the notion of data representation and the need for several choices for data representation is already present in the preliminary architecture [6GDISAC-D22] and retained for the final architecture. In 6G-DISAC, the mobility of targets is supported as this is necessary for the continuity of the sensing service. ETSI currently only considers the mobility of the SRx/STx, which is already present in 6G-DISAC as the set of sensing nodes is dynamic ([6GDISAC-D22] and [6GDISAC-D41]).

The role of semantics in the architecture is not in the scope of the current mission of the ISG.

2.1.3 IEEE

With the ratification and publication of IEEE Std 802.11bf-2025 [IEEE+25], IEEE has formally established a complete, vendor-interoperable wireless sensing standard. This milestone transforms Wi-Fi from a pure data-connectivity technology into a dual-purpose sensing platform. By

leveraging existing WLAN waveforms and fine-grained channel state information (CSI), 802.11bf enables:

- Human presence and activity recognition
- Gesture classification and fall detection
- Device-free localization and tracking
- Respiration/heartbeat monitoring
- Environmental mapping, imaging, and 3D skeletal reconstruction

An overview of the standard is provided in [IEEE+25+DU] addressing both sub-7GHz and 60 GHz and lists their shared features, similarities, and differences.

Figure 2-5 shows the sensing procedure in 802.11bf, as described in [802.11bf+25], while Table 2-1 describes the role of each component of the architecture.

Figure 2-5: Sensing procedure in IEEE 802.11bf.

IEEE 802.11bf supports multiple sensing topologies, including monostatic configurations where the transmitter and receiver are the same device (such as a single access point performing radar-like sensing), bistatic setups with one transmitter and a separate receiver, and multi-static arrangements that involve one or multiple transmitters and multiple receivers, providing the richest sensing information. To enable these configurations in a unified and interoperable manner, the standard introduces entirely new MAC-layer protocols, such as Sensing Measurement Setup, Triggered Sensing Sounding, and Sensing Measurement Reporting, which coordinate measurement, sounding, and data exchange across devices from different vendors, a capability that did not exist prior to 802.11bf.

Table 2-1: Key Roles in 802.11bf architecture

Role	Description	Typical Device(s)
Sensing Initiator	Starts/stops sensing sessions, configures parameters, collects results	Wi-Fi AP or capable STA
Sensing Responder	Performs measurements, optionally processes raw data into results	Any participating STA/AP
Sensing Transmitter (Tx)	Transmits sensing signals (usually triggered NDPs or other sounding frames)	One or more STAs/APs
Sensing Receiver (Rx)	Measures reflections/CSI from the transmitted sensing signals	One or more STAs/APs
Sensing Client	Application-layer entity that requests and consumes final sensing results	Phone, cloud server, hub, etc.

Relation to DISAC architecture

The IEEE network architecture is very different from that of 3GPP and hence architectural choices made in 802.11bf are not directly transposable. However, the phases in a sensing procedure have some similarities: sensing capabilities exchange, sensing measurement session, sensing measurement exchange, and sensing measurement session termination. [6GDISAC-D22] has discussed the need for exchange of capabilities in particular for UEs. There is no sensing session in ISAC but an activation and deactivation of a given sensing service.

2.2 DISAC in the context of 6G architecture and semantics

As mentioned in the introduction to section 2, the principal focus of the current sub-section is on positioning Distributed ISAC in the overall 6G architecture and in exploring the application of semantics to the DISAC architecture. The 6G-DISAC project has already investigated and applied some concepts from the HEXA-X-II project and this investigation is updated in this document. On semantic aspects, a joint workshop was held between 6G-DISAC and 6G-GOALS in Bari, at the Polytechnic University, on July 2025 and an effort to extract synergy between the projects has been made. Note that both the above projects are also mentioned already in [6GDISAC-D22].

There are several initiatives on ISAC in the framework of SNS projects and some of them work on architecture. Evaluating all these projects was not feasible, given the allocated time and resources for this task. Furthermore, public deliverables are not yet made available for several of these projects. Hence, overall comparison of DISAC with other SNS ISAC architectures was not realizable in the timeline of 6G-DISAC WP2.

This section provides a quick overview of Hexa-X-II and 6G-GOALS, focusing on topics of interest for this deliverable and highlighting eventual synergies and differences.

2.2.1 Hexa-X-II

[6GDISAC-D22] had already examined and used a few concepts from the localisation and sensing deliverable of the Hexa-X-II project [HEXAXII-D33], while extending them beyond what was present in that deliverable by, for instance, providing a clear separation between control and data functions i.e. the sensing management and the sensing processing functions. In this section, the work done by Hexa-X-II to fit ISAC into a broader 6G picture is examined. It should be noted that Hexa-X-II uses the term JCAS rather than ISAC. JCAS is a component of what is called “Networks beyond communication” which also includes other bricks like “Exposure

and Data Management”, “Compute Offloading Protocols, Signalling, and Procedures” and “Application- / Device- driven optimisation and enhancements for Beyond Communication Services” (see Figure 2-6).

Figure 2-6: Hexa-X-II “Networks beyond communication”: layers and functionalities.

The above figure shows the principal layers defined in Hexa-X-II which are:

- Network Functions Layer (NFL): consists of functions in the UE, RAN, the core and the transport network. Beyond Communication functions are also included in this layer.
- Network-Centric Application Layer (NCAL): consists of functions centred on the network capabilities and can interact with the control plane of the NFL to provide enriched services to vertical applications. The functions at this layer can provide certain actions/updates to the network functions and thereby provide quick ways to modify the network functionality, enabling optimization of the network.
- Application Layer: represents the applications that may have certain service expectations from the network. The applications make use of the NCAL through an exposure function/interface.
- Pervasive Functionalities block: refers to those functionalities and frameworks that operate at the various layers of the 6G E2E system, and can interact with all the different layers, as well.

Relation to DISAC architecture

The layering approach and the terms used for these layers by Hexa-X-II have been adopted for the DISAC architecture in this deliverable. The preliminary DISAC architecture (see Figure 3-1) focuses on the NFL. The SeMF and SePF are Beyond Communication network functions at the NFL.

In this deliverable, functional blocks at the NCAL have been added to support multi-modal sensing in the DISAC architecture. The pervasive functionalities box of Hexa-X-II has been extended to include generic semantic components and models.

2.2.2 6G-GOALS

6G-GOALS introduces a goal-oriented, semantic-aware framework that bridges semantic-aware Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven decision models with Open RAN (O-RAN) principles,

addressing the significant gap from traditional bit-level communication paradigms to semantic communication paradigms [6GGOALS-D25]. The 6G-GOALS architecture is depicted in Figure 2-7.

Figure 2-7: 6G-GOALS Semantic-Aware architecture.

Key Innovations:

1. **Semantic Communication Paradigm:** By leveraging semantic-aware modules at the UE and application sides, namely the **Semantic Module** and **Semantic Extractor**, the architecture allows extracting semantic content from raw data to identify data conveying *meaningful and contextually relevant information*, reducing bandwidth consumption and latency.
2. **O-RAN Semantic Integration:** 6G-GOALS extends the **O-RAN architecture** with semantic-aware functionalities through the **Semantic RAN Intelligent Controller (S-RIC)**, which enables semantic processing of exchanged data at both Near-Real-Time (Near-RT) and Non-Real-Time (Non-RT) layers. Furthermore, **enhanced Y1 and novel Y2 Interface** capabilities support bidirectional semantic data exchange between RIC and edge/cloud platforms, unlocking new opportunities for edge/cloud intelligence, and distributed AI.
3. **Distributed AI and Real-Time Decision Making:** The architecture incorporates distributed AI models that empower the network to self-organise, anticipate changes in traffic patterns, and optimise resource distribution dynamically. With **rApps** and **xApps**

running on the S-RIC, the system achieves *predictive analytics*, *context-aware processing*, and *autonomous optimization*, setting up a new standard for resilient and intelligent RAN operations.

4. **E2E Semantic Communication and Sustainability:** Through the Semantic State Representation Function (SSRF), the architecture enhances semantic awareness in the 5G Core (5GC) network operations, enabling goal-oriented resource management, and adaptive policy enforcement. At the same time, this e2e design is coupled with a focus on **energy efficiency** and **sustainable operations**, driven by AI-powered decision models that minimise unnecessary transmissions and prioritise critical data flows.

Relation to DISAC architecture

The discussions during the joint workshop with 6G-GOALS enriched the understanding of the use of semantics in the context of O-RAN. From the architecture perspective, this deliverable proposes to make use of semantics, not at the network functions layer but at the NCAL layer. No direct use of any blocks or components from 6G-GOALS has been made. This deliverable also defines and adds a semantic plane which is not present in 6G-GOALS.

3 Extensions to the preliminary DISAC architecture

The preliminary DISAC architecture was described in [6GDISAC-D22] and it is briefly presented below as an easy reference.

Figure 3-1: Preliminary DISAC architecture from [6GDISAC-D22].

The SeMF receives sensing service requests from a sensing application, which is typically an AF but it can be a UE or a NF. The SeMF is responsible for the discovery, selection and configuration of the sensing nodes (STx and SRx, RIS, etc.) in the sensing service area. The SePF takes care of processing the sensing measurements for tasks like target detection, localisation, and tracking.

Several extensions to the above preliminary version are proposed below that help complete the DISAC architecture. The first extension deals with the support of multi-modal sensing i.e., of non-3GPP devices along with the ISAC/DISAC-based sensing. This brings several challenges and a proposed solution using semantics as described below in section 3.1.1. The concept of a semantic plane has been defined and described in section 3.1.2. The function blocks are at the NCAL layer (see Figure 2-6) and section 3.1.3 describes the different function blocks and the interactions between them.

In DISAC architecture, UEs can act as sensing nodes (STx/SRx). This brings several challenges such as energy consumption, typically limited compute power, and also the mobility of the UEs must be considered. Some of these issues have been investigated in [6GDISAC-D22]. The second section 3.2 explores different modes of communication and orchestration in the context of collaborative sensing, where multiple UEs are involved and need to exchange data with each other to provide a sensing service.

The topic of data representation has been described in [6GDISAC-D22]. The focus was on the impact of data representation on communication costs, where the challenge is to reduce the volume of data to be exchanged between the SRx and the SePF. With UEs, computation cost is a major challenge. Section 3.3 provides an overview of different approaches that take into account both computation and transmission. In addition, the paradigm of “Compute-while-transmitting” has been explained and its impact on the architecture described.

3.1 Semantics for multi-modal sensing in the DISAC architecture

The first phase of intelligent distributed processing in 6G-DISAC deals with sensing in the mobile network (ISAC) where the sensing devices are elements of the network (UEs, base stations and RISs). This architecture is described in [6GDISAC-D22]. In this deliverable, the intelligent distributed processing is extended to include multi-modal sensing, by integrating devices such as cameras, LiDAR, radar which act as sensors. [LJH+25] uses the term Multi-modal Integrated Sensing and Communication (M-ISAC) for such integration. A major challenge for M-ISAC is the heterogenous nature of multi-modal data with a diversity of data formats, temporal resolution, continuous stream or discrete packets and so on. The use of semantics to tackle this unification problem is an option that is being actively explored as shown in the first section. In particular section 3.1.1 provides some pointers on how extensions of Large Language Models (LLMs) can be used as a base for semantic representation. A key takeaway is the imbrication of AI with semantics, and this is described in section 3.1.2 which provides an overview of the AI plane and introduces the concept of a semantic plane at an abstract level. Finally, section 3.1.3 provides a concrete instantiation of the abstract semantic plane that supports semantics based multi-modal fusion. It shows where these planes fit in the layers, as described in section 2.2.1. Section 3.1.3 also describes functions in the semantic plane and the interfaces between these components and the functions at the network and applications layers. Thus, section 3.1 describes a major new extension to the preliminary DISAC architecture.

3.1.1 Multi-modal fusion and semantics

Information fusion for multi-modal data involves the extraction and subsequent integration of the most relevant and complementary information from diverse data sources, producing a unified representation that is richer, more informative, and better suited for various application scenarios. For instance, by combining multiple sensing modalities, such as point cloud, imagery, radar, and acoustic data, the accuracy and robustness of vehicle detection and tracking can be significantly enhanced, especially in challenging Non-Line-of-Sight (NLoS) conditions [RJT+23].

The semantic communications technology enables the transformation of complex raw multi-modal data into meaningful semantic representations, facilitating compression and efficient transmission. Complementarily, multi-modal data understanding techniques extract essential contextual and scene information from diverse inputs, such as video, imagery, and sensor data, enabling comprehensive analysis and intelligent decision-making. Semantic-based approaches can enhance the entire data processing pipeline by enabling precise data fusion, comprehensive understanding, and optimised multi-task processing. As an example, AI-driven multi-modal ISAC can achieve robust feature alignment, dynamic environment modelling, and intelligent beam management, while enabling adaptive resource allocation between sensing and communication can promote distributed knowledge across the network. The integration of intelligent multi-modal sensing and communication systems has emerged as a promising direction to augment sensing outcomes with refined semantic interpretation. However, data generated from multi-modal-ISAC sensors and communication devices exhibit diverse formats, semantic structures, latent representations, and time-frequency characteristics, which complicate effective fusion.

To overcome these challenges, the incorporation of AI is essential. LLMs further enhance semantic comprehension, providing contextual learning and efficient reasoning over high-dimensional multi-modal datasets. LLMs have been adapted to multi-modal data and these Multi-modal LLMs (MLLMs) have been used in ISAC [CZD+25, LJH+25]. In these works, multi-modal encoders are proposed, followed by different approaches attempting to unify modalities. [CZD+25] proposed an input projection layer (linear projection, Q-formers, or cross-attention mechanisms) after the encoder to unify the representation (see Figure 3-2). [LJH+25] leveraged a pre-trained modality encoder and pre-trained LLMs with knowledge of the modalities integrated through learnable connectors or specialized expert models in a specific interface, mapping heterogeneous inputs to versatile outputs.

Figure 3-2: Framework of the MLLM-enabled ISAC system (from [CZD+25]).

The convergence of multi-modal sensing ISAC and semantic fusion marks a transformative step towards intelligent, self-aware networks. By combining distributed sensing, semantic reasoning, and AI-driven communication, these systems evolve from data-level observation to semantic-level understanding. Promising candidates for exploiting this integration and improving interpretability, scalability, and energy efficiency are identified in LLM-assisted multi-modal reasoning and semantic alignment methods, coupled with edge-optimised deployment.

However, neither of these papers [CZD+25, LJH+25] investigate the integration of semantics in the overall ISAC architecture.

3.1.2 Semantic plane

Modern wireless network architectures, such as 5G, are built upon the fundamental concept of distinct "planes" to efficiently manage and optimise various network functionalities. This architectural separation, notably between the Control Plane and the User Plane, was introduced to enhance scalability, flexibility, and reliability by decoupling network management from data forwarding. The Control Plane is dedicated to handling all signalling, session establishment, mobility management, and resource allocation, essentially dictating how the network operates (e.g., the AMF in 5G). Conversely, the User Plane (or Data Plane) is solely responsible for the high-throughput, low-latency transmission of actual user data, carrying the content of communications (e.g., the User Plane Function (UPF) in 5G). This clear division allows for independent optimization and scaling of network management versus data transport.

Figure 3-3: Holistic view of AI native in 6G [NOK+2025].

Building upon this established architectural paradigm, the AI/ML plane, as discussed within 3GPP, represents a fundamental architectural evolution where AI/ML capabilities are deeply integrated into the core network functions and interfaces. Nokia's vision extends this concept further, envisioning AI/ML capabilities deployed everywhere across the entire network ecosystem, creating a truly pervasive intelligent infrastructure as shown in Figure 3-3 [NOK+2025].

This plane is designed to enable intelligent network operations, including dynamic resource management, predictive maintenance, anomaly detection, and automated optimisation, moving beyond traditional rule-based systems. In the future, this sophisticated AI/ML plane will profoundly impact semantic communications by providing the intelligence required to understand, interpret, and act upon the meaning of transmitted information, rather than just the raw data. It will allow networks to infer user intent, prioritise critical semantic content, and dynamically adapt communication parameters to ensure the most efficient and effective delivery of meaning, thereby enhancing communication efficiency, reliability, and user experience by focusing on the value of information.

Figure 3-4: Conceptual illustration of semantic plane operation within 5G network architecture.

Further extending this concept, the semantic plane is introduced as a new conceptual layer specifically designed to leverage the intelligence of the AI/ML plane. This semantic plane focuses on understanding and processing the meaning and intent of information. It relies heavily on the computational power and intelligence of the AI/ML plane, which encompasses the entire lifecycle from data collection and feature extraction to model training, deployment, and continuous testing. By leveraging these AI/ML resources, the semantic plane can perform dynamic signal adaptation and carry out semantic interpretation and instruction generation. These capabilities enable more intelligent network operations, such as adaptive backhaul transmission and context-aware signal processing optimisation, ultimately improving network efficiency and responsiveness to varying communication and sensing demands.

Figure 3-4 illustrates a 6G-DISAC vision example of how the semantic plane could be integrated into the existing 5G network architecture [3GPP-TS23.501], showing its interaction with the AI/ML plane [3GPP-ETSI-2025] and the underlying network functions to enable semantic-aware communication and control. The detailed relations and links between these different entities will be further elaborated in the next section 3.1.3.

3.1.3 System-level semantics in DISAC architecture

The preliminary deliverable [6GDISAC-D22] focused on semantic communications at the physical layer (semantic waveform) and at the RAN level. Based on the introduction provided in section 3.1.1, a system-level contribution on the role of semantics to help fulfil sensing service requirements is provided hereinafter.

In DISAC, sensing data is received from multiple modalities and from devices over a large area. Several sensing applications will typically run in parallel over this extended area and each of them will have different objectives. In the research literature, most articles are focused on semantics at the link level or E2E for individual devices or at network level such as O-RAN. There are very few papers addressing system-level use of semantics as discussed here. One may note the survey paper [WHF+25] which addresses the semantic-aware communications paradigm which aims to address the synergy between several agents or swarm type collaboration. However, the papers cited under semantic-aware communications either do not consider the cooperation among multiple agents or do not take the semantic representation into account.

A high-level description of such a semantic-enabled system is provided in Figure 3-5 which provides a concrete instantiation of the abstract semantic plane illustrated in section 3.1.2.

The semantic plane is in the middle of Figure 3-5 in the NCAL layer. It consists of three network functions: Semantic Sensing Fusion and Representation (SSFR), Semantic Sensing Goals (SSG), and Semantic Sensing Orchestration (SSO). The interfaces associated with these three functions are labelled as SN1, SN2, SN3, SN4, SS1, SS2 and SA1 respectively¹. The close link between the semantic and AI planes, which was highlighted in both sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2, is shown as well.

The naming convention for the interface labels is as follows: the first letter is S, which stands for the semantic plane, the second letter is the layer/plane to which the interface connects (N for the network layer, S for the semantic plane and A for the application layer). The one exception is SA2 which connects to the Sensing Exposure Function (SEF), which is in NCAL), but the destination of the exposed information is to the sensing applications in the application layer.

Figure 3-5: System-level semantics for sensing.

The SA1 interface allows the sensing application to communicate the sensing service requirements to the SSO.

The SN1 and SN2 interfaces connect the SSO to the Other Sensing Devices Management Function (OSDMF) and the SeMF, respectively. It is meant for control and management. It serves to communicate the sensing service requirements and for control operations, such as changes in sensing parameters.

The SN3 and SN4 interfaces are for the data collection entities (SePF and OSDMF) to send the processed sensing data to the SSFR. This component performs semantic fusion and unifies the diverse data formats to a semantic representation, as discussed in section 3.1.1.

The SS1 interface serves for the SSO to communicate task specific goals to the SSG. The SSO derives these goals from the service requirements.

The SS2 interface permits the dialog between the SSFR and SSG to extract goal-specific sensing information. The SSFR holds global-level information about the sensing system. Each

¹ The labels used in this report are provisional and may be updated as needed to align with the evolving requirements of standardisation.

goal extracts from the SSFR information that is relevant to the goal. The relevant information typically involves a certain zone of the extended area and also particular centres of interest.

Finally, the SA2 interface permits authorised applications to receive the sensing data via the SEF.

This is best explained using the example of the Assisted Parking use case from [6GDISAC-D23]. In this scenario, consider a vehicle moving from an indoor site like an office building to go to a restaurant in town for a business lunch. The application communicates the service requirements to the SSO. The SSO makes use of the semantic framework and contextual information such as street maps to split the overall task into several sub-goals and these are provisioned to the SSG. There are several sub-goals possible in this scenario but, to illustrate the above figure, it's worth focusing on the sub-goal of finding a parking place near the restaurant. The SSFR holds information from both ISAC sensing and non-3GPP sensors for many areas on the town. However, the context here is a specific location (near the restaurant) and a specific centre of interest (parking places). This is the extracted level of representation that is desired by the SSG from the SSFR. Note that the information needs to be soft real time (minutes) regarding the availability of parking places in that sector. This may involve the SSO requesting (via SeMF and OSDMF) to fulfil this transient but precise task. Semantic communication comes into play as this could in turn lead to request the camera applications to focus on parking places in the sector, which leads to more efficient and timely semantic information from the cameras in that locality.

3.2 Role of UE in the architecture and orchestration of the dynamic set of UEs involved in sensing

Notwithstanding the foreseen improvements brought by ISAC in future wireless networks, from an architecture perspective, most of the relevant functionalities may be incorporated into variations of the established systems. For example, BSs acting as STxs and SRxs may be controlled through the O-RAN stack. When considering DISAC, however, system designs that coordinate multiple and heterogenous devices increase in complexity. Progress incorporating environmental devices, such as different types of RISs or passive sensors from the perspective of communications [RISE-D26], [TERRA-D23], [HEXAXII-D23], may be leveraged to provide a unified control interface (under O-RAN or 3GPP standards). However, to fully take advantage of the foreseen DISAC benefits, more considerations are required, as discussed below.

The role of the UE in the DISAC architecture is fundamentally different. In DISAC systems, multiple UEs might participate in the sensing process as STxs or SRxs. Additionally, the collection and distributed processing of the sensing signals necessitate data exchanges between such UEs. Crucially, different from centralised sensing schemes where the single UE has initiated the process and therefore expects results to be sent back, distributed UEs may be called to participate only during intermediate stages of the sensing process without knowledge of the overall procedure (which includes other entities and their role). That is where UE-to-UE orchestration is needed.

Under DISAC, we highlight two ways of UE-to-UE orchestration (as shown in Figure 3-6) considering "transparent" and "non-transparent" inter-device communications. In the first way, from the perspective of a single UE, all other UEs are treated as typical network nodes that offer their available functionalities (STxs, SRxs, LSePFs, SePFs) and their orchestration takes place through the SeMF. In transparent mode, the UEs act as typical 6G RAN nodes that are fully controlled by SeMF and report their data to the SePF. It is important to note that, to provide a common interface between UEs and the SeMF, UE devices might need to be considered as O-RAN nodes (e.g., DUs/RUs) and expose the same interfaces and level of functionalities. The second paradigm can be considered UE-centric. In the non-transparent operation, the

SeMF provides initial setup at the (non-RAN) UEs, who continue their cooperation and data exchanges by individual interfaces without the intervention of the SSO. Given the lower resource availability, mobility, and transient nature of UE devices in networks, it is beneficial for the system to treat with such entities differently from O-RAN-like nodes. This paradigm is better suited to account for the computational and power consumption overheads of the control and data processing schemes and may even support direct UE-to-UE communication without the intervention of the SeMF at certain stages of the sensing procedure [6GDISAC-D41].

Figure 3-6: Two ways of UE-to-UE orchestration.

3.3 Computation and transmission paradigms in DISAC

Considering that distributed nodes are tasked to collect signals, but the end-result needs to be communicated back to the entity that made the original request, various messaging exchanges are necessitated during DISAC systems. The fusion centre(s) and the SePF are tasked with collecting the information and process it to obtain the intended result; however, each SRx, especially ones equipped with LSePFs, needs to determine a policy on how to send its information to the SePF. Two main approaches can thus be underlined, as illustrated in Figure 3-7:

- “Transmit-then-compute:” where each SRx simply transmits the signals it sensed to the SePF that handles all processing.
- “Compute-then-transmit:” where each SRx first parses the locally sensed signals to extract the relevant information and forward it to the SePF, which only fuses information from multiple entities at a higher level.

Evidently, the first paradigm entails much lower computational requirements at the SRx, since the data are only forwarded through transmission without other computational operations being involved. However, high link budgets may be demanded, which may not be readily facilitated in all systems. This is especially true when multiple UEs or other distributed devices are involved in the sensing process. On the contrary, computing before transmitting makes more prudent use of communication resources at the cost of computational requirement demands at the SRxs, which needs to be equipped with reasonably powerful LSePFs. In practice, data can be transmitted by mixing those two ways, where the sensing data are first processed locally to reduce their size and are then transmitted to the SePF for the final computation. This

way necessitates the adoption of predetermined data representation formats suited to each case, as presented in [6GDISAC-D22].

Figure 3-7: Comparison of the "Transmit-then-compute" and "Compute-then-transmit" paradigms.

With the increasing maturity of technologies, such as metasurfaces [AXN+23] and tri-hybrid beamforming [HCD+25] architectures that can shape the form of the wireless channel, a new paradigm might be further introduced: "Compute-while-transmitting" [SDA25]. Under this treatment, the PHY layer is not directly optimised to facilitate high throughput but is rather controlled to perform mathematical operations on the transmitted data that would otherwise need to be performed by LSePFs or the SePF. Leveraging the linearity properties of typical wireless channels that are similar to the operations taking place by neural network layers, "compute-while-transmitting" is particularly attractive for neural-network-based transmissions: the LSePF at the SRx, the SePF, and the metasurface-parameterised channel can be viewed as a Metasurfaces-Parameterised Neural Network (MINN), where the first layers reside in the LSePF, the channel acts as a hidden layer, and the final layers are implemented at the SePF. This practice has the potential of reducing the number of digital layers ultimately implemented by the network entities [SDA25],[HBW+25] and therefore decrease the overall power consumption associated with computation, as well as transmission resources [SA25a], [SA25b], [IAS21]. An overview of this process is given in Figure 3-8 which illustrates over-the-air computing enabled by metasurface-parameterized channels. The computation is split across the sensor device, the SeMF, and the channel, balancing the trade-offs between computational, communication, and power requirements.

Figure 3-8: Compute-while-transmitting under the MINN framework [SDA25].

WP4 of this project focuses on developing relevant protocols and orchestration methods associated to such considerations on distributed schemes. Indeed, both the necessary protocol

requirements allowing sensing and communication among distributed nodes (e.g., UEs), as well as their level of local processing and computation (e.g., whether the distributed node acts as a LSePF) is investigated. Moreover, the underlying problem of resource allocation across such distributed nodes (including computation, in addition to time, frequency, etc.) is discussed. The reader is kindly advised to consult [6GDISAC-D41] for relevant developments.

4 Final DISAC architecture

This section presents the final version of the DISAC architecture.

Important note: though the work on security, privacy, trustworthiness and sustainability is out of scope for the 6G-DISAC project, they are of course critical to an overall ISAC solution. The work being done at ETSI ISAC ISG on “Security, Privacy, Trustworthiness, and Sustainability” will provide a good study of the challenges and potential solutions in this domain.

4.1 Update to architecture based on results from WP4

To support the envisioned DISAC applications, the functions at the NCAL stands as an intermediary interface between the user plane and the physical network entities, the controls of which are exposed by the architecture. The functional view of the architecture indeed provides a unified view of the physical nodes, encompassing heterogeneous devices with different capabilities, requirements, and operation modes. The orchestration of the constituent physical/functional components is therefore of major importance. The development of the algorithms that tackle such goal, which is the focus of WP4 [6GDISAC-D41], addresses the following key aspects:

- **Intelligent Coordination:** Orchestrating multiple devices requires elaborate resource balancing operations. The centralised SeMF is responsible from a high-level overview of the participating devices, their capabilities, and control requirements. The selection of participating devices is an important step of this process and involves balancing different objectives. The functionalities and overheads, that are exposed to the executed algorithms by the functional components, are evaluated to achieve desirable trade-offs [AML+24]. Those are typically related to trade-offs among power consumption for communication, sensing, and computation, allocated network resources (number of antennas, bandwidth, and number of transmission slots).
- **Autonomous or Semi-Autonomous operation:** To reduce the overheads associated with continuous control and information exchange, devices in the network that have sufficient computational capabilities may operate near autonomously. Each such device can be considered as a standalone node of the NFL, equipped with its own LSePF. Under this context, the NCAL is responsible for providing the application parameters and the semi-autonomous devices sporadically report sensing results or communication performance indicators to the SeMF. This mode of operation is particularly attractive for sensing-aided communication tasks [GA25a], [GA25b], where network devices need to perform sensing only to obtain results that will help them reconfigure their operation to support better communication performance. The core distinction is that the sensing information is not transferred to the SeMF, or to fusion centres, thereby preserving user privacy.
- **Adaptability and Reconfiguration:** One of the core responsibilities of orchestration approaches is to ensure the participating devices are able to adapt to changes in the wireless environment. At longer time scales (e.g., when new devices enter or exit the service area), the coordination of these devices takes place at the SSO (see section 3.1.3) entity of the NCAL. However, at small timescales, (e.g., when adapting to fading

variations, user movement, shadowing effects, etc.) the participating devices need to quickly reconfigure themselves to guarantee the desired service requirements (e.g., to change their beamforming patterns) [EDR+25], [SCE23]. The messaging exchanges to support such decisions take place through scenario-specific interfaces within the NFL, without the intervention of the NCAL [SSA25]. The computations required to determine the reconfigurations are physically performed by either the LSePFs of the devices (for distributed schemes) or the SePF (for centralised approaches).

4.2 DISAC architecture

The final architecture of 6G-DISAC is presented below in a manner compatible with other SNS projects, as described in section 2. With regards to the standardisation work in sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2, it should be noted that the architectural aspects of ISAC is still work in progress and no official standards have as yet been published. The work presented is compatible with the current information available with a few exceptions. In 6G-DISAC, the focus is on intelligent and distributed processing and, hence, the need for the distributed sensing processing as described in [6GDISAC-D22]. The standards include support only for centralised processing of the sensing data, whereas DISAC enables distributed processing through the LSePF network function in addition to supporting a centralised approach using the SePF in the core network. Moreover, the semantic aspects of ISAC are not in the scope of the work done in the standards and they constitute a significant new contribution from 6G-DISAC.

The proposed architecture is also in phase with the SNS projects in section 2.2. The overall architecture and use of the layering approach is inspired from [HEXAXII-D33], while, at the same time, extending it as outlined in section 2.2.1 and below. The 6G-GOALS [6GGOALS-D25] work provided the general concepts for the semantic contributions in this project, but the architectural bricks introduced in section 3.1.3 are original contributions from 6G-DISAC.

The DISAC architecture is based on the description detailed in section 3.1.3 on system-level semantics and also on the orchestration options described in sections 3.2 and 3.3. The foundation of the architecture at the network layer was built on the preliminary DISAC architecture [6GDISAC-D22].

Figure 4-1: DISAC final architecture.

Figure 4-1 is similar to Figure 3-5 except that the NFL (3GPP) box is a lot more detailed. This is because the major impact of the new extensions has been on the NCAL layer. The functions in the NFL layer are from the preliminary DISAC architecture. Note also that Figure 4-1 has a legend for the NFL data and control planes. All other interfaces have been described in section 3.1.3.

The primary elements of this architecture shown in the Figure 4-1 are:

- Splitting of the network modules into two layers, the NFL and the NCAL, as explained in section 2.2.1.
- All the network functions in the preliminary DISAC architecture as shown in Figure 3-1 are situated at the NFL, though a different visual representation is used in Figure 4-1.
- Distributed processing is provided by the local SePF. As detailed in [6GDISAC-D22], different types/levels of processing at the LSePF yield different data representations. The processed data is sent by the LSePF to the central SePF, which further processes the sensing data and also performs fusion of information from multiple UEs or other types SRxs.
- SeMF is the central entity, at the NFL, that provides the control and management of the sensing functions. As described in [6GDISAC-D22], this involves the initial selection and negotiation to finalise a set of sensing nodes (STxs, SRxs) that will participate in a sensing service, configuration of parameters and desired data representations.
- Non-3GPP device integration is supported using the standard N3IWF block which provides secure access to the 6G core for non-3GPP access. The OSDMF component plays a role similar to SeMF/SePF and serves as the interface to the semantic functions in NCAL.
- A semantic plane for sensing has been introduced and explained in sections 3.1.2 and 3.1.3. The new NFs in the semantic plane are SSFR, SSG, and SSO which are described in section 3.1.3. The interfaces that connect these semantic plane functions between themselves and to the NFL and application layer have also been described in the same section. These semantic plane functions work together to furnish a semantic representation of sensing data and enable goal-oriented sensing service fulfilment on the one hand and semantic-aware resource management and adaptation of sensing processing to the application needs on the other hand.
- The SSO interacts with the SeMF to provide the adaptability and reconfiguration capabilities needed for efficient orchestration, as described in section 4.1.
- Finally, the consolidated sensing reports are provided to sensing applications that have subscribed to receive these reports through the SEF.

In order to illustrate the description provided above, two sample sequence diagrams are shown below.

Figure 4-2 illustrates the flow in the initial setup of the sensing process. The sensing application sends a sensing request with the sensing service requirements to the SSO and the SSO collaborates with the SeMF to select and configure the sensing devices.

Figure 4-3 shows the sensing data flow from the devices to the sensing application once the sensing activity has been initiated after the setup.

These sequence diagrams are necessarily simplified versions that do not show all the details of the interactions involved and more information on both the process and the interactions can be found in [6GDISAC-D22] and in section 3.1.3.

Figure 4-2: Sensing request setup.

Figure 4-3: Sensing data flow.

5 Conclusions and outlook

This document builds on the preliminary version of the distributed ISAC architecture [6GDISAC-D22] which outlined the key challenges for DISAC and proposed enablers to address them. It situates the DISAC architecture within the broader ecosystem of standardisation efforts and related SNS projects, aiming to contextualise DISAC components within the wider 6G system.

A major extension described in this document is a semantics-based framework for system-wide support of DISAC. This framework leverages the pervasive functions of semantic and AI modules to develop specific DISAC support components at the network-centric application layer. These components generate a comprehensive semantic representation of multi-modal sensing data. Goal functions extract relevant information tailored to specific tasks, while an orchestration block adjusts network parameters as needed, completing a feedback loop. This work provides a high-level overview, with further research required to explore this topic in greater depth. The architecture and network functions defined in the semantic plane of the DISAC architecture are very relevant to the WP5 Assisted Parking use case [6GDISAC-D23] which involves multi-modal fusion.

The role of the UE and its interactions within the architecture, particularly in collaborating with other UEs, is also examined. This facilitates both tight integration of the UE with the architecture (centralised SeMF) and a more peer-to-peer style decentralised approach. These concepts are closely aligned with the objectives of WP4, which considers the protocols and orchestration necessary to support decentralized architectures.

Sensing processing involves computation and transmission, and several paradigms in this domain are described, including over-the-air computation. The implications of these paradigms on architectural elements are also analysed.

Furthermore, the work of standardisation bodies such as 3GPP and ETSI ISG on ISAC architecture has been studied and compared with the proposed DISAC framework. There is broad

convergence and compatibility on key aspects of the DISAC architecture, with some differences noted. From the standardisation viewpoint, the work on DISAC architecture is still evolving. Nonetheless, the work presented here, along with contributions from other bodies and projects, provides a solid foundation for future development.

6 References

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